

DOMESTIC VIOLENCE: THE PROBLEM IS SOCIAL AND LEGAL

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Abstract: This article describes the main problems of domestic violence. We decided to choose this topic because it is very difficult to accept reality and often people, already realizing that something is going wrong, begin to deceive themselves with thoughts that everything is fine. Without stopping the negative attitude towards yourself in time, more serious consequences begin to occur. Considering reality, it is important to distinguish the statement of facts from interpretations. Only by our personal feelings can we understand whether our borders have been violated or not.

Keywords: Domestic violence, physical and psychological violence, family, objects of violence, aggressor, assistance, prevention.

Introduction

At present, the topic of violence, unfortunately, is gaining momentum more and more. Domestic violence is any humiliating behavior that is used for control. Often, pressure begins with a desire to feel control over the victim or with a sense of power over her. Violence exists in all social groups regardless of income, education, social status, class, racial, cultural, religious, socio-economic aspects, i.e. the prevalence of various types and forms of domestic violence is such that covers the entire population. Domestic violence is a real act or threat of intentional physical,

sexual, psychological or economic influence, coercion on the part of one family member towards another in order to control, intimidate or satisfy their needs.

Literature analysis and methodology

The problem of domestic violence has been a taboo area for a long time, and there is still resistance from society to addressing this problem. The Government and international organizations have begun to approach this issue very seriously, various laws in the Family and Criminal Code are being created and improved to protect against violence, and in recent years they have been created: in 1992, the Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination against Women, in its General Recommendation No. 19, stated that violence in discrimination against women is a form of discrimination directed against a woman because she is a woman or has a disproportionate influence on women. Such violence significantly impedes women's ability to enjoy rights and freedoms on an equal basis with men.

In December 1993, the Declaration on the Elimination of Violence against Women recognized that violence against women violates the rights and fundamental freedoms of women, and also called on States and the international community to strive to eliminate violence against women.

In the same year, the Vienna Declaration and Programme of Action recognized that the elimination of violence against women in public and private life is a human rights obligation. The then-existing Human Rights Commission first condemned gender-based violence in 1994 and in the same year appointed a Special Rapporteur on violence against women, its causes and consequences.

In 1995, the UN World Conference on Women, which was held in Beijing, reaffirmed the conclusions of the Vienna conference, calling violence against women one of the most important problem areas.

In 2017, the Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination against Women celebrated the 25th anniversary of General Recommendation No. 19* by developing further international standards in the field of gender-based violence against women. In General Recommendation No. 35, the Committee on the Elimination of

Discrimination against Women recognized that the concept of the inadmissibility of gender-based violence against women is gradually acquiring the status of one of the principles of customary international law, imposing obligations on all States.

In February 2017, a resonant law on the decriminalization of beatings in the family began to take effect.

Domestic violence against a woman is not a simple quarrel or conflict where both partners have an equal position in a critical situation. There is no equality in domestic violence. One person seeks to control the other by using physical force, economic opportunities, psychological pressure, etc. in order to gain power and control over his partner.

Results and discussion

The relevance of this problem is determined by statistics. According to data on the global prevalence of violence by the World Health Organization (WHO), every third woman (35%) in the world is physically or sexually abused by a partner throughout her life. Worldwide, 30% of women who are in a relationship say that they have experienced some form of physical or sexual violence from their partner during their lifetime. According to the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, all people have the right to live without violence. No one should tolerate torture or degrading acts.

Within family violence, separate categories can be distinguished, such as: child abuse; violence directed against a spouse; violence against the elderly, etc. The peculiarity of violence in the family context – for both the rapist and the victim – is the need to continue communication, maintain and maintain a system of interpersonal relationships.

The causes (factors) of domestic violence are divided into:

psychopathic (predisposition to violence of parents and children); social – the impact of external (social) factors; poverty, unemployment, social isolation, low educational and cultural level, etc.; psychosocial (factors of violence are divided into structural, situational and communicative; communicative factors are

defining).

There are four main types of domestic violence : psychological, physical, sexual and economic violence. A specific case of domestic violence may include all four types, several or one of them. These types can also alternate in time and move from one to another.

Women have been victims of violence for significant years and continue to be subjected not only to physical but also psychological consequences. In addition, women who face domestic violence may resort to alcohol and drugs as a coping mechanism, eventually becoming addicted to such substances.

The affected parties also experience physiological damage, up to the development of serious diseases. Results of domestic violence they have a very detrimental effect not only on their psychological, but also on their physical health. First of all, domestic violence begins with the fact that the partner wants to feel that he is in control of the relationship. The abuser focuses on intimidating the other partner, using nonverbal, verbal or physical techniques to eventually gain control over the other person. In order for the other person to fulfill their desires, the oppressor may also resort to the use of emotional violence. Emotional abuse includes verbal abuse such as name-calling, shouting, shaming, and accusation.

Isolation, bullying, and controlling behavior are equally categorized as emotional abuse. The perpetrator can isolate the victim from friends and family or manipulate them by forcing they think that they, and only they, are to blame for the violent behavior. As noted above, it is not necessary that violence be only physical, it can also be emotional, which is much more common. In contrast to physical violence, emotional violence is more insidious and imperceptible. The main purpose of such violence is to make a person doubt himself and other people, to break his will. Victims of emotional violence are people who find themselves next to the aggressor and attract his attention with some of their virtues, which he wants to appropriate. The victim tends to justify the partner's behavior, tries to deceive herself with positive thoughts, and in many cases thinks that the partner is acting badly

towards her because of a lack of joy and understanding in life. The aggressor is always an experienced and talented player. As a result of interaction with such a person, the victim is left alone with difficult feelings and, as they say, falls into the abyss and cannot find a way out of this situation.

Conclusion

Based on the above, we can conclude that the causes of domestic violence begin with one goal. This goal is set for the purpose of feeling power and control over another person. This is achieved by setting boundaries, isolating the other partner from his friends, family and all loved ones, and even financial control over them. Therefore, to get out of this situation, it is necessary to merge three components: prevention, punishment and assistance to victims. First of all, it is proposed to transfer cases of domestic beatings into the category of frequent public prosecution. This will remove from the victims an unbearable duty for them to investigate the crime themselves. At the same time, it is necessary to legalize the wording "violence against loved ones". Don't be indifferent to each other, stay human in any life situations, and remember, peace on Earth depends only on us! Summing up, it should be noted that whatever the situation of violence, it always causes damage to the development of personality. The consequences of violence are a "psychological time bomb", which includes chronic depression, self-destructive tendencies, difficulties in functioning in the marital and parental roles.

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ГОСУДАРСТВА. Приоритетные направления, современные тенденции и перспективы развития финансового рынка, 260–262. извлечено от

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